

1. **Why are you motivated / excited / required to work on data management / DMPs?**
2. **What are your pain points?**
3. **What do you hope to get out of this workshop?**

Michael Moosberger

1. The major funding agencies in Canada are all moving towards requiring researchers to manage and share their research data more effectively in order to maximize the potential use and re-use of this data by and among other researchers. As a major Canadian university research library we are participating in the Portage Network initiative being developed by the Canadian Association of Research Libraries. The Library is the point organization within the university for making researchers aware of these new still evolving requirements from funding agencies and the tools that are being developed to assist researchers with the management of their research data. We have also taken on a leadership role at our university in advocating for greater open access and are building an infrastructure (institutional research repository, OJS, etc.) to support this.
2. The biggest pain point is trying to build out this new and complex initiative using only the existing human and financial resources available to the Library. Most of the Library staff involved are taking on this work on top of their already full workloads. The second pain point is the general lack of understanding among the university research community in understanding the issues around data management. Many don't understand the Library's involvement in this work and see what is being proposed as just another impediment to them and their research. Gaining the trust of the university research community and showing that we are only there to try and help them will be a significant challenge. The third pain point is about trying to figure out what we actually can and cannot do to assist researchers with their data management issues. Will we have enough computing and storage capacity to meet the needs of all who ask? Can we develop the skills within our team to effectively undertake this work? And what are researchers' expectations going to be of the Library in preserving and managing research data in the long term and will we have the resources to meet these expectations? These are just a few of the issues and pain points that exist for me.
3. A better understanding of what other research institutions are doing to address some of the issues that I've outlined above. To continue to build a network of colleagues to communicate with to discuss ideas; hear about new advances; and get feedback on the development of our own DM program.

Bev Jones

1. DMP gives us a great opportunity to get a little control at the start of the research process, if we could guide the researchers a little more, and get meaningful metadata out of the process it would be so useful throughout the research lifecycle.
2. Researchers need a lot of guidance and do not give granular information unless given specific prompts. They are very keen to copy existing models so, as we are quite small and just beginning, it is hard to get the ball rolling.
3. Sharing of experience. Keen to contribute to metadata agenda. Reassurance.

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Stephanie Simms

1. As a researcher (archaeologist), I experienced constant data management frustration and knew there had to be better ways to, e.g., share data with colleagues in Mexico; design and integrate relational databases and geodatabases; manage unstructured data such as photos and field notes... this led me down an alt-ac path to an interesting job that involves reducing other researchers' frustrations by facilitating better data management practices and writing DMPs that support these practices (not just because they have to). So I think about DMPs all day.
2. The DMPTool is burdened with being a comprehensive data management education platform. Outstanding questions include how to (re)define the scope of the tool and best serve the needs of two primary user groups: researchers and admins/institutions? How to deliver relevant guidance and not overwhelm users? How to monitor changes in data policies for US funders and maintain 33 (and counting) templates?
3. Concrete machine-actionable use cases. All of your ideas!

Daniel Spichtinger

1. As Senior Policy Officer for Open Access one of my tasks is to contribute to the development of our policy in H2020 and beyond. It is therefore important to further develop our approach to DMPs
2. How to reconcile the need to provide a general template in H2020 with discipline specificities
3. Innovative ideas, input for a revision of the DMP template, ideas for the further development of the policy

Rob Hooft

1. I am convinced that good data management can help researchers in data intensive sciences to do better science on a better budget. Since life sciences have become more demanding on data aspects and more data driven, it really pays off to plan data management. The field is so broad that no single person can be experienced in every aspect, and good data management/stewardship tooling (with adequate guidance and pointers) can help people find the right way of doing things.
2. Data Management planning is presented as a stick from funders. The wish to minimize costs of data management, which I do not consider to be costs at all but an investment with great returns.
3. Last year I learned a lot of interesting aspects of data management in your workshop. I love to hear different view points from different stakeholders, to be able to hone my own communications on data management planning. Also I will be very happy to present my view on data management tooling that is really written with the "carrot" in mind rather than the "stick".

Chuck Humphrey

1. I am the Director of the Portage Network, a national initiative in Canada to support libraries in academic institutions to deliver research data management services. One of our national platforms is DMP Assistant, an implementation of DMP Online. As we work with a variety of stakeholders in research data management, including researchers, funders, libraries, researcher service offices, ethics offices, and IT departments, each has discovered value in DMPs. Overall,

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DMPs help communicate the importance of research data to the wider community, guide researchers to best practices in data management, identify levels of service required to support data management and its stewardship, and facilitate the transfer of data from the project level to institutional stewardship.

2. I find the biggest frustration arising from the increased need to share the information in DMPs dynamically with a variety of research stakeholders and their information systems. The information in a plan needs to be liberated from a print-format delivery to a machine-request format that meets the information requirements of those providing research support. This includes the researcher, who also has administrative information needs that should be delivered to her or his DMP. The management and exchange of administrative information in research is a consummate time consumer that distracts researchers from doing research. We should be able to lighten this load.
3. A strategy for turning our DMP platform into a web service that manages and disseminates information about a project's research data and its management.

Rachael Kotarski - British Library and DataCite re3data group member

1. As well as starting the develop the data management processes for British Library data, I am part of the re3data working group - we are excited to find new ways of integrating the tool into the DMP process to support researchers (and institutions) decisions on appropriate data repositories
2. Providing relevant information at the appropriate point for decision making. Providing different levels of information at different points helps to reduce burden, but isn't something that is necessarily easy to tailor
3. Pointers for the re3data group to direct the kind of development that will support the community

Mark Hahnel

1. DMPs stand as a good educational tool for academics who otherwise do not think about data management or reuse of their research outputs. I am hoping that machine readable DMPs will help ensure compliance of policies and mandates and thus drive a cultural shift.
2. We work globally and there are many different flavours of DMPs.
3. Roadmap for a uniform DMP and plans to make them FAIR.

Fernando Aguilar

1. I work on data management in different projects related to Lifewatch, the european Research Infrastructure for biodiversity and ecological research. Besides, my PhD Thesis is oriented to address the whole research data life cycle towards a linked environment based on cloud computing solutions. The use of DMPs in a dynamic way, and, in particular, machine actionable DMPs, can contribute to create a framework where all the different steps on the cycle are connected in a FAIR+R approach.
2. The different stages on the research data life cycle can be manages using cloud computing tools. However, there is no a single tool capable to handle everything, rather than different tools that could be linked (they are not yet): DMP solutions, repositories, DOIs, PIDs, Docker and VMs for

computing, data preservation solutions, etc. DMPs, in a dynamic way, could be the keystone to support and control the different steps.

3. I hope to know other approaches from other communities in terms of DMPs, and how they think is the best way to use DMPs in the near future.

Falco Hüser

1. First of all, our University has just released its data management policy that basically says that all research projects should create a DMP. So it will be very interesting to analyse them and see where there are special needs and challenges. We're also trying to promote Open Science and Open Data as we're really sick of commercial publishers taking over science and misusing the peer-review system. So we want data to become recognized as valuable research output.
2. The structure of DMPonline makes it challenging to implement templates and guidance not related to a funder or an institution (here in Denmark, we have created a "national template" for all universities. We also want to use DMPonline in a more educational way.
3. How to extract information from DMPs for use in the administration for the development of policies and infrastructure.

Peter McQuilton

1. I am excited to work on DMPs as I feel these are a vital piece of research data infrastructure. With 17% of data being lost every year due to being in the wrong format, stored on the wrong media, or simply not having the appropriate associated metadata, DMPs are pivotal to ensure our investment in science is not wasted. As the project coordinator for BioSharing, I want to help life, biomedical and environmental science researchers and data managers understand what resources are out there for their data, and which standards they should use.
2. One of the main problems I see researchers face, and one I experience myself, is simply not knowing what's out there in terms of repositories, secondary databases, data standards and so on.
3. I would like to understand a way forward to integrate or federate domain-specific knowledgebases into DMPs and the DMPTool, either via the use of APIs or other machine-actionable techniques to allow users easy access to the information that they need.

Margreet Bloemers

1. I want to learn more about possibilities of DMP's, to make them really helpful in supporting research and datamanagement. Representing a funding agent (ZonMw, Holland, lifesciences and health research) we work together with universities, univ medical centres, service institutes to find the best way to support researchers with dm (stick? Yes, but also carrot!). A more interactive/actionable DMP fits that goal!
2. Pain points are related to the challenge to help/stimulate the researchers to do good DM, while considering their already heavy workload (in relation to the grant procedures), their (lack of) expertise, etc.
3. Learning about possibilities for the following cases:
 - For a funder like ZonMw, a DMP would gain value when information could be automatically transferred to different IT systems. First, the IT-system of its own

organization for management information and review and monitor purposes. Secondly, the IT-systems of institutions which deliver service (like repositories, catalogues) that facilitate reuse of the dataset.

- For researchers from different institutes and countries, working in one research field, supported by e.g. a JPI of the EU, we want to recommend/require the use of a common research infrastructure (RI) (e.g., a network of repositories, interoperability standards, standard operating procedures, etc). A DMP, tailored for the JPI DMP, leading to the preferred services, would support this goal.

Joshua Finnell

1. As the data librarian for a national nuclear lab in the United States, Los Alamos, my primary role is to help researchers fulfill federal mandates related and contribute to lab policy concerning open data. This role is sometimes complicated by the lab's dual role in both national nuclear science and federally-funded research. In addition to administering the DMPTool, I am also actively involved in building a data repository for the Lab (i.e. institutional Open Science Framework). Like Stephanie, I think and work with data every day.
2. As a standalone product, the DMPTool is a wonderful tool for researchers. However, our goal is to integrate data management planning into the research data life cycle at the lab (which includes review and release of all scholarship produced at the lab). I am particularly interested in case studies or projects where the DMPTool has been integrated into OSF or other repository software.
3. Localized use-cases of customized DMPTool templates and integration of the DMPTool into data repositories and/or research data lifecycle workflows.

Poppy Townsend

1. I work at CEDA (Centre for Environmental Data Analysis) which is one of the Natural Environment Research Council's (NERC) data centres. Within my role here I am solely responsible for the initial scoping/contacting and creating DMPs for NERC funded grants. This eventually leads to archiving their data in suitable formats with supporting metadata on our data catalogue. I'm motivated to try and find a better way to produce more dynamic DMPs that are actually useful for all parties involved (rather than just a box ticking exercise!).
2. Participation and engagement with researchers can sometimes be difficult and I believe there could be better, more linked up ways of creating DMPs for this process. We have recently switched to using a google doc rather than a static word/pdf file; but there is still a lot of effort spent to engage the researchers with this process. Integrating a DMP tool within our existing processes would be extremely important but finding a tool that suits all will be difficult.
3. It would be great to find new ways of creating DMPs that fully integrate and supplement our existing data centre processes; which reduce the current effort involved!

Michel Heeremans

1. As a geoscience research data manager at the Department of Geosciences, University of Oslo, I deal daily with questions related to storage of data. We see that the amount of data researchers use increases dramatically. This causes our researchers to ask for more storage space. To be able to give them that, we either need to buy more space or we can ask them to clean current space

for data from earlier work. The researcher then has the choice to either buy more space from project money or clean. The risk here is, that the researcher will buy cheap USB external storage devices, exposing him-/herself for the risks involved with data loss and poor backup facilities. Making researchers aware of the quickly evolving possibilities in structurally archiving their research data, is an essential factor in making my and my colleagues working day more effective. To write a good DMP will help researchers and IT support personnel to achieve better and effective use of IT resources

2. My main pain point is making researchers motivated to pay more attention on how they use their data. My experience is that many of them do not want to spend too much time on the subject. So, it would help very much if as much as possible in the DMP writing can be automated.
3. I will most probably work tight with researchers developing DMP's in cooperation with the research administration staff. So, for me it is important to keep up to date with modern online DMP technology so we can use the DMP as effectively as possible. In addition, by being involved in this workshop I hope to be able to contribute constructively to develop DMP online tools.

Fernando Rios

1. My perspective is that of RDM service provision at an academic institution. Recently, I've been working, among other things, on figuring out how to integrate research software in RDM workflows. One aspect that has come up is how research software is handled/considered in DMPs. I'm motivated to look at emerging trends for DMP requirements in order to provide more comprehensive data management services
2. When it is mentioned in DMPs, software is generally lumped with data or very little guidance is given on what is required in terms of the software produced as part of funded research. Although there has been some work done to have software management plans as part of DMPOnline, the current offering, while a good jumping off point, appears to be too onerous to complete, considering that researchers already have to think about data. Since data and software depend on one another, Integrating data and (tailored) software-related points in a DMP also makes sense to me. In terms of machine-actionable DMPs, software is an excellent area to explore, given the machine readability of many aspects of software development (e.g., version control, automated builds, etc.)
3. Apart from learning about people's thoughts on machine-actionable DMPs, I hope to be able to contribute some insight into how research software can be better integrated into existing DMPs.

James A J Wilson

1. Whilst DMPs are no longer a major part of my job, in my former life as coordinator of research data management activities at the University of Oxford I offered support to a number of researchers across multiple disciplines, and was involved in developing the institutional version of the DMP Online service and providing training for doctoral students. I was invited to participate in this workshop, and I'm interested in learning about the latest developments.
2. Currently blissfully pain-free, although I doubt this will last for long. I'm leading the development of the RDM infrastructure at UCL at present, and we'll need to integrate DMPs into the wider suite of data management services - in part to assist with capacity planning.

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3. Keeping up to speed with the latest developments and seeing where others - particular researchers - are experiencing frustration.

Jari Friman

1. As a (data)librarian/information specialist at the University of Helsinki, I am one of the coordinators in research data support network at the university of Helsinki. Basically I try to get people from different university units (IT center, library, central administration etc.) to work together for better research data management. I'm also involved in the Finnish Tuuli project in which we have built a national DMP tool DMPTuuli. The tool is based on DMPOnline and DCC is hosting the service for us.
2. In a big, multidisciplinary university it is challenging to build research management services because researchers' needs are so different in different disciplines. Also, the awareness of the usefulness of the DMP varies a lot. Some researchers lack for motivation. They are not familiar with the idea of a DMP and they need to be explained why it is important and why some specific questions are asked. Others work in groups that have their own data managers. They may be frustrated because they don't have infrastructure needed.
3. DMP's could be seen as metadata of research data. It could be a way of disseminating information about research data and Increasing usability and findability. DMP's could be linked to data repositories, for example. It would be easier to market the tool for researchers if we had more to offer than the template and the guidance (which are also important). It would be wonderful if we could show that the tool actually helps you disseminate your research outputs. So, in the workshop I would like to see if this (among other ideas mentioned here) could be implemented in DMP's.

Weiwei Shi

1. I work in the library IT and support digital initiatives such as data repository, institutional repository and long-term data preservation, as well as research data management related applications. University of Alberta hosts and supports Canada's Portage Network DMP Assistant. I don't have work with data management/DMPs directly in my daily work, but I'm eager to see an integrated ecosystem of research data management in the making, allowing DMPs to be the starting point and being able to connect to data repositories, institutional repositories, data discovery systems, and long term data preservation systems.
2. I currently don't have a particular pain point other than the lack of resources to keep up with current development happening in DCC. I would love to see more usability done to the current DMP tools available, and have the true user stories drive future development. And any standard and standardized workflow we can adhere to during the development would make the future maintenance of the integrated system much easier.
3. What do you hope to get out of this workshop?
This is an opportunity for me to see what the front line RDM educators/specialists/users envision the future of DMP tools. I hope the community can come up with coherent and sustainable collaboration plan and strategy so that we can all work together, develop the tool to work with different institutional needs and workflows.

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Peter Neish

1. As Research Data Curator at the University of Melbourne I am tasked with supporting potentially thousands of researchers at my institution. Any tools that can help streamline that for researchers would help enormously. We are trying to couple a DMP tool with our online training, again as a way of minimising the burden on researchers.
2. Getting a picture of research data is not easy. Hoping to get better reporting and analytics out of tools and better integration into other research systems.
3. Seeing what others are doing and learning how DMP tools fit into the research landscape.

Marta Teperek

1. I am supporting researchers with research data management training and services at Cambridge. As part of our service, I'm also assisting them with advice on data management plans as part of their grant applications. I think that DMPs provide researchers with a unique opportunity to think about data management strategy ahead of the project. This motivates them to be pro-active instead of reactive when thinking about their research data management needs.
2. Ensuring that researchers don't perceive DMPs as yet another 'compliance tick box', but as a tool created to help them with effective RDM planning.
3. I hope that integrating DMPs with other university systems and ensuring that they are part of active data management (are with researchers as the data is created and shared), will make DMPs useful tools not only for the University administration (getting out info needed for RDM provision planning), but also for researchers themselves. Perhaps DMPs could be somehow integrated with Electronic Lab Notebooks solutions?
I also wanted to be aware of innovations in this area and hear what others think about the usefulness of DMPs and how we could make them even more effective.

Patrick McCann

1. Most obviously, I previously worked at the DCC as a developer on DMPonline. Apart from that, I work as part of the Research Computing team in the Library at the University of St Andrews, collaborating closely with RDM colleagues. I have a particular interest in software sustainability in support of reproducible research. We encourage the use of DMPonline at the University but struggle to understand the extent to which it is used for real funding applications and the quality of those DMPs.
2.
 - a. As stated above, understanding how DMPonline is being used.
 - b. DMPonline's lack of interoperability, particularly with Je-S, and funder requirements for plans to be in paged document formats - would be great if they required the use of DMPonline and worked directly with it.
 - c. Funders need to demonstrate more clearly that a DMP influences the success or otherwise of an application
 - d. Lack of harmonisation of templates across funders
3. A better understanding of how DMPs, and DMPonline in particular, are developing, and where efforts should be focused in order to achieve the harmonisation and interoperability we need.

maDMPs would seem to provide an opportunity to build feedback loops where good practice results in good DMPs for minimal effort which in turn encourage good practice.

Marisa Pérez

1. The Consorcio Madroño, formed by Universities from Madrid and the UNED are committed to supporting researchers as well as open access. The Consortium has translated DMPonline (PGDonline) which is available to any Spanish-speaking researcher.
2. In order to find solutions to the current problems reported by some researchers, our main points are:
 - a. DMPonline/PGDonline version management
 - b. The possibility of creating a template for projects with many datasets, so common fields only should be copied once.
3. Use case should be interesting in order to learn more about what researchers really need.

William Michener

1. As a faculty member in the University Library, I encourage students and faculty to use the DMP Tool. I also train participants at professional society meetings in creating effective data management plans.
2. Keeping up to date on development plans and maintaining current training materials.
3. Updates on future of the DMP Tool.

Andy Riddick

1. I am responsible for leading our internal teams working on data management planning and data archiving within the British Geological Survey (BGS) . BGS is part of the Natural Environment Research Council (NERC), and hosts the National Geoscience Data Centre (NGDC) – one of several NERC data centres within the UK. Data management planning is a key process both for BGS and for the NERC data centres, ensuring that we can fully document and manage our own internal data resources, and also those datasets donated by recipients of NERC research funding. As NERC data centres we work together on a number of initiatives to improve our data management processes, and are keen to understand and take advantage of new and emerging technologies and tools. I have recently been involved in coordinating a data management planning group across the various NERC data Centres which seeks to improve our data management planning functions across NERC and evaluate appropriate tools including DMP online.
2. One area that we consistently struggle with is the balance between configuring data management plans to capture all the data which we need, but also present the data input forms etc. in a format which encouraging users/researchers to complete them rapidly and efficiently. We're aware that the DMP Online system already offers a number of advantages in this regard, but there may also be potential to link to other systems, for example import data description from project management or other systems, or to harvest DMP data for other purposes is of interest to us.
3. A greater understanding of how machine actionable DMP's work, and also how we could potentially work with the DMPonline/DMP tool teams to provide use cases.

Marie-Christine Jacquemot-Perbal

1. I work at the institute for scientific and technical information of CNRS in France, in a team dedicated to research data management. I think DMP is a key element in data management. It is a pedagogical tool and a means to initiate a dialogue between all the stakeholders who could potentially take part in the management of the institutions' data, from the start of the project design.
2. Too often DMP is still considered as an additional administrative form to fill. In addition, applying the FAIR principles implies for scientists to have acquired new knowledge and skills. Researchers do not have time to spare to build up this new knowledge. However, their engagement to describe in details their experiments is necessary. Our motivation is to facilitate data management by researchers through alleviating their administrative burden, avoiding double capture for example, and taking part in the application of the ICT layer (as "FAIRifier"). Therefore, our aim is to adopt/adapt or develop tools that will render seamless the data management workflow.
3. As DMP could be a connector of the research outputs of a project and people, so DMPRoadmap could be a "connector" between the different services involved at different stages of the life cycle. I am really interested in this workshop as I am convinced of the necessity to make DMPRoadmap evolve toward machine actionable DMP and I am willing to take part in this work. It is also an opportunity to share knowledge, experiences, and country-specific issues

Sophie Hou

1. As the Data Curation & Stewardship Coordinator at the National Center for Atmospheric Research, helping our researchers in meeting their data management requirements, especially those that are part of proposals, is a priority for me. As a result, it is really important for me to understand how to support existing and emerging data management needs, including those from funders/sponsors, more efficiently and effectively.
2. I would really like to help in making it easier for my researchers to learn about data management plan, improve their content over time, track data management progress, and have a positive experience with working on data management.
3. I would like to learn from others and share my own experience regarding DMP, so that I could help in considering any additional advice/recommendations that I could integrate into the data management services at NCAR.

Alex Ball

1. As part of the Library's Research Data Service, I provide advice and guidance to researchers on writing data management plans.
2. Having up to date and accurate knowledge of each funder's (slightly different) expectations and requirements. Ensuring that researchers understand the motivation behind of DMPs, and do actually feel like they have benefitted from the process of writing one.
3. Ideas for integrating DMPs more closely into university processes and systems.

Myriam Mertens

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1. As a research data officer at Ghent University Library, I am part of the team that set up a local instance of DMPonline to facilitate and stimulate DMP writing among our researchers. We are now in the process of establishing a consortium (DMPbelgium) to develop it into a shared tool for research institutions in Belgium.
2. Convincing researchers of the importance and usefulness of writing a DMP, and convincing university policymakers/administrators of the benefits of collecting and analysing DMPs (in terms of the information this can yield). Providing feedback to researchers working in a wide variety of domains.
3. Learning more about machine-actionable DMPs and DMP Roadmap, and exploring ideas for DMP integration with other systems (e.g. could they be used to demonstrate compliance with data protection regulations, for example by populating an institution's internal data processing register, which is required by the GDPR?).

Thilo Paul-Stueve

1. I am the central data manager of a German university. We are developing central services for data management with support for data management planning being one of them.
2. There are no real pain points, but there is still a lot of work to do in Germany. Currently, German universities all develop their training and consulting on their own. There are nationwide networks and activities regarding research data management. In the framework of the German Initiative for Network Information (DINI) working group Research Data there will now be a sub-working group for data management planning with an inaugural meeting in the end of March. There will be an interest group for DMPonline.
3. I am interested in exchange. I like to learn more about the new DMP Roadmap. And I like to know more about machine-actionable DMPs. At our university we are working on Data Policy Kit that will support automation with regard to data access and publication. I am curious what are the differences and similarities to machine-actionable DMPs.

Daniel Mietchen

1. I am interested in integrating research workflows with the Web to facilitate collaboration amongst and between humans and machines. Data form a key component of such workflows, and data management plans can assist in handling research data all along their life cycle.
2. DMPs are often treated as yet another bureaucratic layer in the research ecosystem, while their potential to actually make research more efficient through better data management remains largely untapped.
DMPs are usually neither machine actionable nor properly versioned nor public. In contrast, in ever more contexts of our lives, it is becoming routine to have almost instant and occasionally even user-friendly access to information about things of interest. Take trains, for example: in many areas, the course of railways and the location of train stations along the way can easily be looked up using various means, and the same goes for time tables and itineraries as well as for delays or detours. Basically any person or machine can look that up for any train, be they on a train or not. Now replace the trains by research objects like data: their whereabouts are typically only known to their train's driver and not, e.g., to the stations or to drivers of other trains, at

least not until months or years have gone by. I see machine actionable, versioned and public DMPs as a way to move research closer to the transport scenario and beyond.

I am not aware of anyone having tested the extent to which aggregation of multiple DMPs or parts thereof could provide new opportunities to discover and engage with the underlying data, including at scale.

3. Getting a better overview of what others are doing in this space.

Ideas for next steps in terms of assessing the usefulness of DMPs that are any, neither or all of machine actionable, versioned and public.